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PERSONNEL MANAGER'S PERSONAL INADEQUACY LEADS TO ORGANISATIONAL STRESS – AN SYSTEMATIC STUDY

Dr.V.Sumathy¹

Dr.G.S.Subashini²

Abstract

Stress is a physiological reaction to certain threatening environment and is caused by events in the work environment. Stress can play a positive role at the workplace by increasing the attentiveness of the staff and activating their capacities. A moderate level of stress at workplace has the potential to add towards the organization's efficiency. But it becomes precarious once excessive level of stress begins to affect one's health and productivity. It is often assumed that managers and executives are more vulnerable than non-managers to the ravages of stress. Executive burnout is often the end result of stress experienced, but not properly coped with, by an executive (Pareek, 1983). The research model proposed by Bhagat S.R (2010) depicts the three facets of organizational stress (i.e. Personal Inadequacy, Role Ambiguity, Role Conflict, And Role Overload) that are antecedents of psychological strain which, in turn, is negatively related to job satisfaction, job involvement, and organizational commitment.

Key words: personnel, Personal Inadequacy, organisational stress, UdaiPareek.

Introduction

Stress is defined as a non-specific response of the body to any demand made upon it, which results in symptoms such as rise in the blood pressure, release of hormones, quickness of breath, tightening of muscles, perspiration and increased cardiac activity. Stress is not necessarily negative. Some stress keeps us motivated and alert, while too little stress can create problems. However, too much stress can trigger problems with mental and physical health, particularly over a prolonged period of time. - Marzabadi E A, Tarkhorani H.

Classification of Stress

For better understanding of stress, let us classify it under two broad categories

A. General Stress

1. **Positive Stress:** Accordingly positive stress is that 'stress' or 'pressure' or 'emphasis' which induces, or results in, a positive change in shape, understating, intensity of emotion and action.

i. Special importance on some Object/Thing/Event/Goal/Person etc:

Feeling of love and hate make somebody or some people very important to us who in turn influence our attitude and actions. They make us channelise our energy towards such people with different amounts of pressure.

ii. Enthusiasm:

Enthusiasm is putting in extra hours of work, devoting extra time for a cause, and endure extra pressure which one believes to be worth enduring.

iii. Sense of achievement and recognition:

It is said that for those who are willing, the sky is the limit it results in positive stress that inspires a person to achieve and get recognition.

2. **Negative Stress:** Beyond a limit, when either the desired results are not achieved or an individuals feels overwhelmed and the sense of achievement are replaced by cynicism, despondence a sense of dejection and a general worthlessness.

B. **Specific Stress:** If the general stress is grounded in interpretation and belief the specific stress derives its identity from the source of origin and effect (perceptible as well as imperceptible) on the specific individual being. Accordingly specific stress has several sub-types. i.e.

i. **Physical Stress:** Any prolonged physical discomfort causes stress to the biological body.

ii. **Mental Stress:** Thoughts, memories, beliefs, attitudes and interpretation of events are primary sources of mental stress.

iii. **Emotional Stress:** Human beings are basically emotional beings. Positive emotions make us surmount the toughest times.

iv. **Professional/Economic Stress:** This back to the basics, i.e., matters of survival. It is not only the choice of one's vocation, but also factors like the pay packet, promotional avenues, placement, travel, man-hours, skill, gadgets, boss, subordinates, peers, dynamics of organizational

¹ Assistant Professor, Department Of Business Administration, M.R. Government Arts College, Mannargudi.
² Assistant Professor, Department Of Business Administration, Kuthavalaachiyar Government Arts College For Women(Autonomous), Thanjavur

goals vis-à-vis individuals ambitions that matter a lot in causing stress.

- v. **Miscellaneous/Environmental Stress:** There are miscellaneous factors like a secret desire, spiritual curiosity, living space, traditions and customs to be observed, religious beliefs etc. that cause anxiety which in turn affects ones physical, mental and emotional stress.

Sources of Stress

Advances in technology mean that a personal office and desk are no longer considered essential for management to function. There are numerous factors to consider when determining the presence of stress in the workplace, the most common being listed below.

Excessive working hours/unrealistic deadlines/inordinate workload

Long working hours required by many employers can take a toll on an employee's health. Most individuals can work at an excessive pace for a short period of time but in the event that an employer expects this to be continuous, it can lead to devastating results – for example, burnout of the employee, which can possibly lead to early retirement or hospitalisation and the necessity for the organisation to find a replacement at short notice.

Work 'under load'

Job 'under load' associated with repetitive routine, boring and under stimulating work has also been associated with ill health. Particular groups of workers such as pilots, air traffic controllers and nuclear power workers face a special aspect of work 'under load'. They must deal with long periods of time in which they have little to do, but facing the possibility that they may suddenly be required to spring into action in a crisis.

Impact of new technology

Employees can be faced with sudden change, often without receiving the necessary technological support and training from their employing organisations. They are expected to become their own administration centers, with the computer network server being the controller. Long gone are the days when an employee experienced day-to-day interaction with colleagues – and this form of communication is fast becoming obsolete. Inevitably, this can have a profound negative effect on job performance.

Fear

Members of the workforce might be too frightened to admit they are experiencing stress-related problems in case they are viewed by their employers as weak and

unable to cope – and, therefore, possible candidates for the next round of redundancies.

Uncertainty and change

Although both are part of industrial life in the 21st century, many managers find their organisation handling of such matters to be unrealistic and unacceptable. Redundancy can have devastating and far-reaching effects on all personnel, both for those staying and those leaving the organisation.

Short-term contracts

Common in today's business world, employees in the public, private and corporate sectors have to accept that they may have to tender for their own jobs and deal with the outside competition. For many, this represents a completely new role – one that can cause high levels of uncertainty and financial worry. No longer is there such a thing as a 'job for life'.

Changing role

Employers now expect employees to do 'more for less' in terms of people, finance and equipment, and have unrealistic expectations of their employees. When given additional responsibilities, they are not necessarily given the appropriate support and training. Many employees feel that they are no longer treated as people, and they lack both autonomy and clear direction from the management.

Changing culture

Paternalistic organisations died some time ago, and there is now a growing gulf between what people want from their jobs and what they get. The 'presenteeism' factor is alive and well – particularly in organisations where there are threats of redundancy. Many employees feel the need to be seen in the workplace at all times if they are to justify their existence (whether or not they are actually being productive).

Crisis and trauma

Employees in fields such as the emergency services are at special risk from the effects of trauma and post trauma stress. Their employers should acknowledge the emotional support they need and act in a tangible way. But the effects of a crisis can happen in any organisation: an accident at work, an accident at home, the death of a family member or a suicide in the workplace. These sensitive situations need to be dealt with and not become taboo subjects that will take the organisation a long while from which to recover.

Bullying at work

A report published by the University of Manchester Institute of Science and Technology (UMIST) in 2001

found that one in four people had been bullied within the last five years and that bullying may contribute to the loss of as many as 18.9 million working days annually.5 Clearly it is bad for business and affects teamwork, enthusiasm and morale.

Objectives

To find out the association between stress and Personal Inadequacy(PI).

Sources Of Data

Primary data is collected from officer's cadre employees by using a standard format Questionnaire.

Universe

Researcher planned to study the role stress of all employees from Madras Cements Ltd, So that the universe is definite population.

Sampling

The researcher collected data from 110 officers (out of 124) by using purposive / convenience sampling method.

Instrument For Data Gathering

ORS scale was developed by UdaiPareek(1982). The ors scale contains five items for each role stress (a total of 50 statements); it uses a point scale. (0- 'If you never or rarely feel that way', 1- 'If you occasionally feel that way', 2-'If you sometimes feel that way', 3 -'If you frequently feel that way', and 4 -'If you always feel that way', respectively)

The instruction for this scale are as follows :

"People have different feelings about their roles. Statements describing some of them are given below. Use the answer sheet to write your responses. Read each statement and indicate, in the space against the corresponding number in the answer sheet, how often you have the feeling expressed in the statement in relation to your role in the organisation. Use the numbers given below to indicate your own feelings. If you find that the category to be used in answering does not adequately indicate your own feelings, use the one which is closest to the way you feel. Do not leave any item unanswered."

Total score of ORS ranges between 0 - 200 and on each role stress ranges from 0 to 20. A simple summation of the scores of the subject o each role stress would indicate the scores on that dimension. Pareek (1982) has identified the following ten stressors based on organisational roles.

1. Inter-Role Distance (IRD)

IRD refers to the conflict between the organisational role and other roles. When an individual occupies

more than one role there are bound to be conflicts between the different roles that he occupies. (Item nos 1, 11, 21, 31, and 41).

2. Role Stagnation (RS)

RS takes place when an individual feels there are few opportunities for learning and growth in the role. In organisation which are fast expanding and which do not have any systematic strategy of manpower development , managers are likely to experience this stress (Item nos 2, 12, 22, 32, and 42).

3. Role-Expectation Conflict (REC)

REC means conflicting demands made on the role by different persons in the organisation. One may receive conflicting expectations from the boss, subordinates, peers or clients. (Item nos 3, 13, 23, 33, and 43).

4. Role Erosion (RE)

RE is a feeling that some important functions a role occupant would like to perform are being performed by some other person. This happens when organisations are redefining their structure, wherein it may lead to elimination of some roles and creation of new ones. This may prompt managers to feel that new role is less important than the previous role. (Item nos 4, 14, 24, 34, and 44)

5. Role Overload (RO)

Role overload is the result of large variations between the expected output and actual output. When role overload is high neither the delegation process non-assistance, is useful towards role performance. (Item nos 5, 15, 25, 35, and 45)

6. Role Isolation (RIs)

RI emanates due to lack of linkages between one's role with other roles in the organisation. In a role set, a role occupant feels that certain roles are psychologically closer to him due to frequency and ease of interaction. When linkages are strong, the role isolation will be low and in the absence of it, role isolation is felt high. Therefore role isolation can be measured in terms of the existing and the desired linkages (Item nos 6, 16, 26, 36, and 46)

7. Personal Inadequacy (PI)

When a role occupant feels that he is not prepared to undertake the role effectively, he may experience this stress. The role occupant may feel that he has not had enough time to prepare for the assigned role. Persons who are assigned new roles without enough preparation or orientation are likely to experience this type of stress. (Item nos 7, 17, 27, 37, and 47)

8. Self Role Distance (SRD)

This stress arises out of the conflict between the self concept and the expectations of the role, as perceived by the role occupant. (Item nos 8, 18, 28, 38, and 48)

9. Role Ambiguity (RA)

When an individual is not clear about the various expectations that people have from his role, he experiences this type of conflict. It may be due to lack of information or feedback to the role occupant. Role ambiguity may be in relation to the activities, responsibilities, priorities, norms or general expectations. Sometimes role ambiguity may emanate out of occupying roles which are newly created in an organisation. (Item nos 9, 19, 29, 39, and 49)

10. Resource Inadequacy (Rin)

This stress is experienced due to non-availability of resources needed for effective role performance. These may be information, people, material, finance or facilities. (Item nos 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50)

Personal Inadequacy and Age

Age	High	Medium	Low	Chi-square value	d.f.	Significance
20-30	12	33		75.698	6	0.000
30-40	9	20				
40-50	4	15	6			
50-60			11			
Total	25	68	17			

Observing the frequency distribution of PI level based on age, it is identified that specific role stress increases with the increase in age. Majority of the respondents 63.6 percent reported medium level of PI and 22.7 percent

To identify whether there is any significant difference in the PI based on age, Chi-square test is used, from the result, Chi-square value is found to be 75.698 and significance value is 0.000 at 6 d.f. So, it is concluded that there is significant difference in the PI perceived by employees differ significantly at 1% level. It is also found that there is increase in PI with increase in Age.

Personal Inadequacy and Qualification

Qualification	High	Medium	Low	Chi-square value	d.f.	Significance
Diploma	7	16		27.336	4	0.000
UG		23				
PG	18	29	17			
Total	25	68	17			

Observing the frequency distribution of PI level based on qualification, it is identified that specific role stress increases with high qualification. To identify whether there is any significant difference in the PI based on Qualification, Chi-square test is used, from the result, Chi-square value is found to be 27.336 and significance value is 0.000 at 4 d.f. So, it is concluded that there is significant difference in the PI perceived by employees differ significantly at 1% level. It is also found that there is increase in PI with High Qualification.

Personal Inadequacy and Designation

Designation	High	Medium	Low	Chi-square value	d.f.	Significance
Trainee	10	39		100.474	6	.000
Officer	9	26				
Deputy manager	6	3	3			
Manager			14			
Total	25	68	17			

Observing the frequency distribution of PI based on Designation, it is identified that specific role stress increases with the changes in Designation. To identify whether there is any significant difference in the PI based on Designation, Chi-square test is used, from the result, Chi-square value is found to be 100.474 and significance value is 0.00 at 6 d.f. So, it is concluded that there is significant difference in the PI perceived by employees differ significantly at 5% level. It is also found that there is decrease in PI with high level of Designation.

Personal Inadequacy and Department

Department	High	Medium	Low	Chi-square value	d.f.	Significance
Personnel		22	11	128.960	18	.000
Quality Control		13				
Mines		2				
Mechanical	5	4				
Instrumentation		15				
Electrical	4	1				
Stores	3	9				
Time office	13					
Finance			6			
Production		2				
Total	25	68	17			

Observing the frequency distribution of PI based on Department, it is identified that specific role stress increases with the changes in Department. To identify whether there is any significant difference in the PI based on Department, Chi-square test is used, from the result, Chi-square value is found to be 128.960 and significance value is 0.000 at 18 d.f. So, it is concluded that there is significant difference in the PI perceived by employees differ significantly at 1% level. It is also found that there is increase in PI with Changes in Department.

Personal Inadequacy and Years of Experience

Years of Experience	High	Medium	Low	Chi-square value	d.f.	Significance
Below 1 Year	7	20		128.960	18	.000
1-10	9	43	6			
11-20	9	4				
21-30			5			
31-40			6			
Above 40		1				
Total	25	68	17			

Observing the frequency distribution of PI level based on Years on Experience, it is identified that specific role stress increases with the Decrease in Years on Experience. To identify whether there is any significant difference in the PI based on Years on Experience, Chi-square test is used, from the result, Chi-square value is found to be 85.881 and significance value is 0.000 at 10 d.f. So, it is concluded that there is significant difference in the PI perceived by employees differ significantly at 1% level.

Personal Inadequacy and Income

Income	High	Medium	Low	Chi-square value	d.f.	Significance
5,800	3	3		191.061	32	0.000
6,800		4				
7,000		6				
8,500	4					
9,000		7				
10,000		9				
12,000		12				
14,500		8				
15,000	12	3				
16,000		4				
18,000	1	10				
21,000	5					
26,000			3			
30,000			6			
35,000		2				
36,000			5			
70,000			3			
Total	25	68	17			

Observing the frequency distribution of PI level based on Income, it is identified that specific role stress increases with the increase in Income. To identify whether there is any significant difference in the PI based on Income Chi-square test is used, from the result, Chi-square value is found to be 191.061 and significance value is 0.000 at 32 d.f. So, it is concluded that there is significant difference in the PI perceived by employees differ significantly at 1% level.

Personal Inadequacy and Marital Status

Marital Status	High	Medium	Low	Chi-square value	d.f.	Significance
Bachelor	7	33		14.819	2	.001
Married	8	35	17			
Total	25	68	17			

Observing the frequency distribution of PI level based on Marital Status it is identified that specific role stress high for Married people. To identify whether there is any significant difference in the PI based on Marital Status Chi-square test is used, from the result, Chi-square value is found to be 14.819 and significance value is 0.001 at 2 d.f. So, it is concluded that there is significant difference in the PI perceived by employees differ significantly at 5% level.

PERSONAL INADEQUACY AND NUMBER OF FAMILY MEMBERS

Number of Family Members	High	Medium	Low	Chi-square value	d.f.	Significance
Two		6		16.534	8	.035
Three	9	19	12			
Four	12	26	5			
Five	4	15				
Six		2				
Total	25	68	17			

Observing the frequency distribution of PI level based on Number of Family Members it is identified that specific role stress is high for Increase in Family size. To identify whether there is any significant difference in the PI based on Number of Family Members Chi-square test is used, from the result, Chi-square value is found to be 16.534 and significance value is 0.035 at 8 d.f. So, it is concluded that there is significant difference in the PI perceived by employees differ significantly at 5% level.

Most Contributing Variables for Organizational Stress

Fig. 1 : Most contributing variables for organisational stress

From the above bar chart we came to know that Role Erosion(RE), Role Stagnation(RS), Inter Role Distance(IRD) and Personal Inadequacy (PI) are the most contributing variables of organisational role stressors, RA and REC variables are the least contributing variables for organisational stress. Other variables like RI, RIN and RO place in middle.

Findings Related To Personal Inadequacy (PI)

- From statistical inferences 22.7% of respondents with high level of stress, 61.8% of respondents with medium level of stress, and 15.5% of respondents with low level of stress with PI.
- There is a significant association between PI with Age.
- There is a significant association between PI with Education.
- There is a significant association between PI with Designation.
- There is a significant association between PI with Department.
- There is a significant association between PI with Years of experience.
- There is a significant association between PI with income.
- There is a significant association between PI with marital status.

- There is a significant association between PI with Number of family members.

Conclusion

Every employee must be responsible for his/her own well-being and must do everything to combat stress. A stressed individual will be ineffective not only as an employee but also as a person. A stressful working experience can adversely affect the other facets of one's life. Ultimately, therefore, every individual must be responsible for not allowing stress to enter into his/her life. A stress free life is a happy life.

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